

Evaluating the Influence of Marketing Channels on the Economic Well-being of Milk Producers in India

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Abstract

The Indian dairy sector plays a pivotal role in rural livelihoods, significantly to income, food security and social welfare. This study examines the impact of marketing channels choices on the welfare of milk producers in India. Despite being the world's largest producers of milk, India faces disparities in milk productivity and the economic outcomes of its dairy farmers. Leveraging the data from the 77th round of The National Statistical Office (NSO), the research analyse the performance of the four primary marketing channels: cooperatives, private collectors, other households and miscellaneous traders. Employing multivalued treatment effect model and multinomial logit framework, the study identifies critical socio-economic and institutional factors influencing channel selection. The findings highlight significant variations in price realization, milk volume and total income across channels. Private channels emerge as the most lucrative, offering the highest returns per litre, while cooperatives provide stability through fair pricing and structured support. Conversely, informal channels, such as direct sales to households, often yield lower substantially enhance milk producers income and expenditures compared to informal alternatives. This paper underscores the importance of organized marketing system in improving rural livelihood, recommending policy interventions to enhance infrastructure, promote cooperative participation and integrate private players more effectively. By addressing market inefficiencies, the study aims to bridge the income gap among dairy farmers and support sustainable rural development.

Key words: *Livestock, marketing channels, welfare, milk producers, dairy cooperatives*

Introduction

India being a milk deficit nation in 1950's and 1960's, India has evolved into the self-sufficient country with surplus production (Gulati and Juneja, 2023). India's most significant achievement in transforming from a milk-deficient nation to a milk-surplus one was the "white revolution". Over the years, it propelled the country to a leading position and had a profound impact on its livestock (Bhargav et.al., 2022). Since 1970, the livestock sector's contribution to the India's agricultural gross domestic product has steadily increased, marking one of the most significant shifts in the structure of the country's agricultural economy was due to Operation Flood implemented by the National Dairy Development Board (NDDB),

which helped in connecting rural milk producers with urban consumers via an extensive network of dairy cooperatives (Mishra et al., 2022) From 2012 to 2023, the share of the livestock sector in Agricultural GDP rose from 21.8 per cent to 30.2 per cent (National Account statistics, GoI, 2024). Livestock rearing, particularly dairying, has played a crucial role in securing both food and income for rural households (Birthal et. al., 2014). The growing significance of the dairy sector within the agriculture economy has been a key aspect of India's agricultural transformation (Kumar et.al., 2019). Around 88 per cent of livestock in India is owned by families with holdings of less than 4 hectares (Annual Report, GoI, 2020). The contribution of livestock are evident at the household level through its role in boosting income, ensuring food security, and improving social status (Bailey et al., 1999). The livestock sector provides support for the livelihoods of a significant portion of rural households in the country and can play a key role in strategies aimed at reducing rural poverty. The dairy industry is regarded as the backbone of the Indian rural economy, with millions of resource-limited farmers engaged in this sector (Das, et al., 2020). India remains the world's leading producer of milk, yet its milk productivity is relatively low, averaging around 4.3 kg per animal per day. . In fact, the annual milk yield per dairy animal in India is just half of the global average (Kumar et al., 2013). The Indian dairy industry has seen significant transformations, marked by a substantial rise in milk production. This growth is attributed to two key factors: the increase in population of dairy animals and enhanced productivity per animal (Annual Report, GoI, 2020). Further, the variations in milk production levels can be linked to the uneven distribution of high-quality breeding livestock, differences in availability of resources for feed and fodder, disparities in animal healthcare services, and access to artificial insemination facilities (Kumar et.al, 2011). Moreover, in India, dairy farming is not always a commercial activity. The 40 per cent of milk-producing households do not sell milk (Vandeplas et.al, 2013). Instead, there has been steady rise in the consumption of milk and milk products among Indian households. The demand of milk and its product has been increased from 36.2 kg per annum in 1983 to 66.9 kg per annum in 2022-23. The growing demand for milk in urban areas, combined with the abundance of milk producers in rural regions, has drawn both organized and unorganized players into the milk industry. The unorganized sector comprises wholesalers, sweet shops, milk vendors, and the producers themselves, while the organized sector includes private and cooperative dairies (Makarabbi et al., 2023). Dairy cooperatives are essential to the country's organized milk marketing system. Despite this, the average size and scale of village-led dairy cooperatives have remained largely unchanged (Bardhan and Tewari, 2007). Approximately 80 per cent of milk sold continues to flow through traditional channels, dealing with raw milk and conventionally processed products.

With the Liberalization economy of India in 1991, the dairy sector has also allowed private processors to compete more directly with both traditional markets and cooperatives handling processed milk. As a result, numerous private milk processing companies have entered in the line of dairy market. Additionally, since late 1991's, the role of supermarkets and retail chains has significantly expanded in the Indian market, including sale of milk. The role of marketing channels is critical in any production sector, but it becomes even more significant for small-scale milk producer due to the perishable nature of raw milk. In India, as

in other developing countries, both “direct” and “indirect” marketing channels coexist for the distribution of milk, making the choices of the right channel crucial for producers (Mishra and Goyal, 2015). Securing reliable market channels is essential for dairy farmers to gain economic advantage from milk production by ensuring they receive fair and profitable price (Mohapatra et al., 2022). The role of marketing chain has received significant attention, leading to recommendations for improving efficiency and lowering transaction costs (Anandaraj, 2015).

It was well established that the marketing channels played a significant role between milk producers and final consumers. The recent past growth of agriculture and allied driven by the livestock sector (Chand and Singh, 2024), and it is the second larger source of farmers income. The study aims to explore how different marketing channels affect the welfare of milk producers in the country. The study evaluates the various distribution channels through which milk is sold, including traditional markets, cooperatives, and their implication on the economic welfare of producers. The core objective of the paper is to assess how the choice of these channels impacts key welfare indicators such as income, milk value, milk sale price etc. of milk producers. Using a multinomial logit model, the paper estimates the determinants of marketing channel choices while accounting for socio-economic variables, access to market information and institutional factors. The study also analyses welfare differences across marketing channels. It also highlights the quantity of milk sold through different channels of distribution in both quantity and monetary terms. Finally the paper will provides the policy recommendations aimed at improving milk producers access to profitable markets and enhancing welfare through better infrastructure and market integration.

Data and methodology

This study using household data of 77th round of The National Statistical Office (NSO), which conducted a survey, between 1st January 2019 and 31st December 2019, on “Land and Livestock Holdings of Households and Situation Assessment of Agricultural Households” in the rural areas of India. In the first visit of this survey 58040, and in second (revisit) 56899 households were covered. We replicate only those households that survived in both visits and were involved in agriculture activities only. With these conditions, final 44735 households were selected and out of them 10215 household’s sale milk, so the final data set is 10215 households.

Major four channels were found to sale of milk. Our aim is to assess the impact of channel choice on farmers welfare which highly influenced by the endogeneity problem. As a result, the model choice to analyse is important, so we apply the semi-parametric “Multivalued Treatment Effect model “MVT” as used in the literature (Cattaneo, 2010; Imbens, 2000; Wooldridge, 2010). This model is an extension of the propensity score matching model for a binary decision choice to the case of multiple choices. The estimation process of the model proceeds in two stages.

First stage: Modelling farmers’ choices of marketing channels to sale the milk

Four different marketing channels are specified to sale the milk. Following the conventional wisdom from the literature on discrete choice models, the multiple choices of farm marketing channels are specified as the Multinomial Logit Model (MNL model) by taking value 1 to milk selling to other any place, 2 to those selling to co-operatives, 3, and 4 respectively to other households, and private channels. The probability of each farmer's marketing channel choice can be specified as follows

$$p_j = \frac{\exp(X'\beta_j)}{\sum_1^4 \exp(X'\beta_j)}, j=1,2,3, \text{ and } 4$$

Where, p_j is the probability when the farm uses the j^{th} type of marketing channel X' is a vector of explanatory variables that are associated with farm welfare indicators, and β_j are the parameters to be estimated. The consistent estimates can be obtained using the Full Information Maximum Likelihood (FIML) estimation method. With the consistent estimates of the MNL model, the study has calculated the predicted probability of each marketing channel that a farm would choose.

Stage second: Modelling the milk sellers' welfare indicators' equations

This step estimates the milk sellers' welfare indicators' equations. Our welfare indicators comprise i. Milk output quantity, ii. Total value of milk output, iii. Milk price, iv. Monthly Income of the household, and v. Monthly consumption expenditure. In this stage, we only observe a welfare indicator if a specific marketing channel is chosen to sale the milk. Since, the choice of a particular marketing channel is not randomly selected; selectivity bias may occur (Cattaneo, 2010). This can be eliminated by adjusting for confounders. The estimator of the second-stage outcome equation proposed by Cattaneo (2010) is introduced as follows: Let Y_j is the farm welfare indicator and K_j is the indicator if a farm chooses the j^{th} marketing channel ($j=1, 2, 3, \text{ or } 4$ corresponding to each farm marketing choice). X is a vector of covariates, and (Y_j, K, X) is observed for the i^{th} farm. The treatment status of each farm is as

$$D_j K_j = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } K_j = j \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

where $D_j (K_j)$ is the binary indicator for a farm to use the j^{th} farm marketing channel. Given the selection on observables and common support condition assumptions (Cattaneo, 2010), the conditional expectation on the farm profit for choosing the j^{th} marketing channel can be identified by the conditional expectation of observed outcomes for farms of that choice. After defining the generalized propensity score, mean of potential outcome is identified by weighing the observed outcome through conditional probability of received treatment.

Table 1: Description of the variables used in the study

Variable	Descriptions
Dependent Variable	
Other any channel	1 if the milk producer sell milk through any other channel, and 0 otherwise
Co-operatives	1 if the milk producer sell milk through co-operatives , and 0 otherwise
Other household	1 if the milk producer sell milk through other households, and 0 otherwise
Private collector	1 if the milk producer sell milk through private collectors, and 0 otherwise
Independent Variables	
Technical information	1 if the milk producer have the technical information, and 0 otherwise
OBC	1 if the milk producer belong to OBC category, and 0 otherwise
General	1 if the milk producer belong to general category, and 0 otherwise
Male	1 if the milk producer is male, and 0 otherwise
Bank account holder	1 if the milk producer is the bank account holder, and 0 otherwise
MGNREGA card	1 if the milk producer is working under MGNREGA card, and 0 otherwise
Animal health card	1 if the milk producer is has Animal health. card, and 0 otherwise
KCC Holder	1 if the milk producer has Kisan credit card, and 0 otherwise
Education	Education level of the milk producer in ordinal scale from 1 to 2
Number of milking animals	Represents the number of the total milking animals owned by the milk producers
Welfare Variables	
Milk Price	Per litre price of milk received as sale outcome
Milk output quantity	Quantity of milk produced in litres
Milk Output Value	Total amount received from milk sale in Rs
Household Income	It is the average monthly income of the households obtained by summing the net income (after deducting the <i>paid out and imputed expenses</i>) obtained from crop, livestock, wages and salaries, pension and remittances, leasing out the rent, and income from non-farm business.
Household Expenditure	It is the average monthly expenditure of the households

Source: Authors compilation.

The table 1 provides the detailed summary of the variables employed in the study, which capture marketing practices, socio-demographic variables, government support, and the economic circumstances of the milk producers in India. These variables are divided into three categories: dependent variables, independent variables and welfare-related variables. The dependent variable in this study is “marketing channels” a multinomial variable indicating the choice of marketing channel used by the milk growers, coded as follows: 1 for other channels, 2 for cooperatives, 3 for other households and 4 for private collector. The diverse socio-economic characteristics of milk producers are expected to influence their choice of marketing channels differentially.

Results and discussion

The dairy sector in India plays a crucial role in rural livelihoods, with millions of small-scale producers relying on it as primary source of income. Marketing channels, such as cooperatives, private firms, and informal markets, act as vital links between producer and consumers. The choice of marketing channel significantly affects the welfare of milk producers, influencing their income. This study examines the economic outcomes of various marketing channels on milk producers, focusing on price realization, milk efficiency etc.

Figure 1: Milk sale in different channels as percentage of total sale

The figure 1 illustrates the percentage of milk sales through different marketing channels, including cooperatives, other households, private entities and “other” channels. Cooperatives dominate the milk marketing landscape, accounting for nearly 38 per cent of total sales. This highlights their crucial role in ensuring stable income for milk producers, as cooperatives often provide fair pricing, reliable payment systems and support services, which positively impact producers welfare. Other households represents 25 per cent of sales, suggesting a substantial portion of milk is sold directly to consumers or neighbouring households. This method offers producers flexibility in pricing and direct consumer interaction, although it may lack the formalized benefit of cooperatives. The private sector, encompassing companies and individuals, makes up around 20 per cent of sales. Private companies may offer better price but often come with stricter quality standards and more competitive environments. Lastly, the “other any” category, contributing only 8 per cent includes small traders and local vendors indicating their minor role in overall milk sales.

Table 2: Total Milk sale, Value of quantity sale and average price of milk sale among sale destinations

Sale Destination	Qty (lakh litter)	Value (in Rs. Crore)	Price realised (Rs. litter)
1: Co-operatives	53.41	16.37	30.6
2: Other household	39.01	14.33	36.7
3: Private	36.92	19.66	53.3
4: Other any	11.82	4.06	34.4
Overall	141.15	54.42	38.6

Source: Authors estimation, using Situation Assessment of Agriculture Households Survey, 2019.

The table represents the distribution of milk sales by Indian producers across various marketing channels and highlights the impact on their welfare through price realization, quantities sold and the total revenue. The marketing channels include cooperatives, other households, private buyers and general category labelled “other”.

The estimated milk quantity sale and value of sale in the survey, to cooperatives account for the largest quantity of milk sales at 53.41 lakh litres, contributing Rs. 16.37 crore in total value. However, the price realized per litre is relatively low, at Rs. 30.6, indicating that while cooperatives provide stable and substantial market for producers, they might offer lower prices compared to other channels. Further, sales to “other households” represent the second-largest channel, with 39.01 lakh litres sold, values at Rs. 14.33 crore. Interestingly, the price per litre realized here is significantly higher, at Rs. 36.7, suggesting that direct household sales might allow producers to earn more on per-unit basis, possibly due to the absence of intermediaries or better market conditions.

The private buyers channel, although accounting for a lower quantity of milk at 36.92 lakh litres, provide the highest per litre, at Rs. 53.3, resulting in a total value of Rs. 19.66 crores. This channel is the most lucrative for milk producers, demonstrating that private enterprises, perhaps due to their greater purchasing power or fewer regulatory constraints, offer the best monetary returns per unit. Another is “Other” category, with the smallest quantity of milk sales at 11.82 lakh litres, generates Rs. 406 crores in value. The price realization here stands at Rs. 34.4 per litre, slightly below the household sales but higher than cooperatives, offering a middle-ground opportunity for producers. Overall, the total sales amount to 141.51 lakh litres, generating Rs. 54.42 crore with an average price realization of Rs. 38.6 per litre. This average reflects the varying degree of benefit milk producers based on the marketing channel they chose, with private buyers offering the highest returns and cooperatives providing stability despite the lower prices.

The diverse socio-economic characteristics of milk producers are expected to influence their choice of marketing channels differentially. Hence, table 3 provides the comprehensive comparison of socio-economic and production related variables, revealing how these factors differs across marketing channels. Each variable’s mean value is provided, with the standard error shown in parentheses, offering insights into the distribution of these characteristics across the sample of milk producers. The average age of milk producers is

fairly consistent across all the channels, ranging from 51.39 years (Private) to 52.35 years (other any). The overall mean age is 51.91 years, suggesting that milk production in these regions is generally handled by middle-aged individuals with minimal variations between channels. Further, education level, represented by schooling years, vary slightly among the marketing channels. Producers in the “other any” category have the highest average schooling years (5.5 years), while those in the Co-operatives have the lowest (5.08 years). The overall mean schooling years is 5.26, indicating a relatively low level of formal education across the sample. Another variable is household size which is relatively uniform, with an overall average of 5.17 members. The highest household size is associated with the “Other household” channel (5.23), while Co-operatives have the smallest average household size (5.02). This suggest that larger household sizes may slightly influence marketing channel choices but not significantly. Furthermore, all the milk producers across all the channels have access to a bank account, with a uniform proportion of 0.98 across categories, indicating financial inclusion among the sample.

Table 3: Summary statistics of the explanatory variables used in the study

Particulars	1: Co-operatives	2: Other household	3: Private	4: Other any	Overall
Age	52.26 (0.264)	51.98 (0.206)	51.39 (0.237)	52.35 (0.394)	51.91 (0.127)
Schooling year	5.08 (0.098)	5.32 (0.077)	5.23 (0.087)	5.5 (0.142)	5.26 (0.047)
Household size	5.02 (0.049)	5.23 (0.04)	5.18 (0.043)	5.22 (0.07)	5.17 (0.024)
Bank account	0.98 (0.003)	0.98 (0.002)	0.98 (0.002)	0.98 (0.005)	0.98 (0.001)
KCC	0.15 (0.008)	0.2 (0.006)	0.25 (0.008)	0.26 (0.013)	0.21 (0.004)
MGNREGA	0.37 (0.01)	0.34 (0.008)	0.38 (0.009)	0.41 (0.015)	0.37 (0.005)
Animal Health card	0.03 (0.004)	0.01 (0.001)	0.02 (0.003)	0.01 (0.003)	0.02 (0.001)
Information Access	0.45 (0.01)	0.24 (0.007)	0.43 (0.009)	0.27 (0.013)	0.35 (0.005)
Inmilch animal	2.07 (0.066)	1.63 (0.02)	1.97 (0.029)	1.69 (0.041)	1.84 (0.019)
Total animal	13.4 (0.944)	13.96 (1.154)	15.92 (3.204)	13.39 (1.408)	14.34 (1.055)

Note: values in parenthesis is standard error of mean value

Source: Authors estimation, using Situation Assessment of Agriculture Households Survey, 2019.

Ownership of KCC, which provides credit access to farmers, increase from 15 per cent in the Co-operatives to 26 per cent in the “Other any” category, with an overall average of 21 per cent. Another variable if MGNREGA participation, approximately 37 pe cent of milk producers participate in the Mahatma Gandhi Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA) scheme overall. The involvement in supplementary employment programs varies slightly across marketing channels. Further, access to animal health cards is generally low across all the categories reflecting the limited adoption of this important health resource. Information access varies significantly across channels. Co-operative members have the

highest access (45 per cent), while “other households” members have the lowest. Overall 35 per cent have access to important market and production information. Another variable is inmilch animals, the average number of inmilch animals is 1.84 across all producers. Co-operatives members have the highest average while “other households” channel has the lowest, indicating differences in the livestock productivity based on marketing channel choices. Further, the total animals owned by the producers shows greater variation, with the highest average in the Private channel (15.92) and lowest in the Co-operatives (13.4). the overall average is 14.34, indicating that private channel producers tend to have larger herds.

Table 4: Estimation results of the marketing channels equation with marginal effects: multinomial logit model

Particulars	dy/dx	Coefficient	Std.	z	P>z [95%]
Co-operatives					
Technical information	0.009	0.733	0.081	9.100	0.000
OBC	0.011	0.545	0.096	5.680	0.000
General	0.013	0.132	0.108	1.220	0.222
Male	0.017	0.030	0.145	0.200	0.838
Bank account holder	0.028	0.604	0.260	2.330	0.020
MGNREGA card	0.009	-0.219	0.078	-2.800	0.005
Animal health card	0.038	0.876	0.290	3.020	0.003
KCC Holder	0.010	-0.627	0.093	-6.750	0.000
Education	0.001	-0.017	0.008	-2.070	0.038
Number of milking animals	0.003	0.127	0.028	4.490	0.000
Constant		-0.448	0.302	-1.480	0.138
Other household					
Technical information	0.010	-0.167	0.078	-2.140	0.032
OBC	0.013	0.140	0.087	1.620	0.106
General	0.015	0.008	0.096	0.090	0.931
Male	0.020	0.046	0.134	0.340	0.730
Bank account holder	0.036	0.391	0.226	1.730	0.084
MGNREGA card	0.011	-0.279	0.072	-3.880	0.000
Animal health card	0.033	-0.465	0.323	-1.440	0.151
KCC Holder	0.012	-0.357	0.081	-4.400	0.000
Education	0.001	-0.008	0.007	-1.050	0.293
Number of milking animals	0.004	-0.041	0.030	-1.370	0.170
Constant		1.072	0.267	4.010	0.000
Private					
Technical information	0.010	0.724	0.078	9.250	0.000
OBC	0.012	0.583	0.093	6.270	0.000
General	0.015	0.190	0.104	1.830	0.068
Male	0.018	0.210	0.144	1.460	0.144
Bank account holder	0.035	0.292	0.242	1.210	0.227
MGNREGA card	0.010	-0.114	0.075	-1.520	0.129
Animal health card	0.035	0.326	0.295	1.110	0.269
KCC Holder	0.012	0.027	0.084	0.320	0.751
Education	0.001	-0.016	0.008	-2.030	0.042
Number of milking animals	0.003	0.099	0.028	3.540	0.000

Constant		-0.248	0.286	-0.870	0.387
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Source: Authors estimation.

Dairying has emerged as a significant income source for millions of poor and rural households, playing a vital role in creating employment and income opportunities (Sharma and Kalamkar, 2021). Therefore, the marketing channels- co-operatives, other households and private are crucial determinants of milk producer's welfare, affecting their income, access to resources and overall well-being. By examining the marginal effect of key variables helps to better understand the factors guide milk producers decisions. The table 4 presents the estimation of marketing channels equation using a multinomial logit model, focusing on the marginal effects (dy/dx) for various factors influencing the choice of marketing channel among milk producers. So, the choice of co-operatives as a marketing channel is significantly shaped by access to technical information, with producers having such resources showing higher likelihood of opting for co-operatives. This reflects the importance of knowledge in fostering trust and participation in structured channels. Producers from OBC category also exhibit a strong preference for co-operatives, highlighting the channels inclusivity for disadvantaged groups. However, the general category shows a positive but statistically insignificant association ($p=0.222$), indicating variability in preference among caste groups. Gender, particularly male producers, does not significantly effect this choice.

Ensuring reliable marketing channel is essential for dairy farmers to maximize the economic gains from milk production (Kaur and Toor, 2024). Examining the observed mean value of welfare indicators in a traditional manner may lead to inaccuracies, as it fails to consider specification biases (Table 5). This section evaluates the effects of marketing channel choices both before and after adjustment for these biases. The observed mean reflects the average value of a welfare indicator without factoring in selection bias, while the adjusted mean accounts for this bias to provide a more accurate assessment. The table presents an analysis on welfare indicators, such as milk price, milk value, milk quantity, total income and monthly expenditure, across different marketing channel.

Milk Sale price

The observed mean price of milk varies significantly across marketing channels. After accounting for specification bias, private channels show a significant positive change in the adjusted mean price (6.48, 16.70 per cent), indicating their ability to fetch the highest returns. Co-operatives also displays a moderate improvement, it fetches 3.35 per cent higher price, ensuring fair prices. However, household selling milk to "other households" experience a slight decline of 0.49 per cent, suggesting inefficiency in pricing through informal exchanges.

Milk Value

The adjusted mean value of milk increases substantially for co-operatives by 22.50 per cent and for private channels it increased by 16.54 per cent. This indicates that these channels are effective in maximizing the economic returns from milk sales. Conversely, selling to "other household" leads to a negative to a negative change in value leads to decline by 3.18 per cent, reflecting lower efficiency in capturing milk's value.

Table 5: Estimated results of the welfare indicators across different marketing channels

Marketing channels	Observed mean	Adjusted Mean	SE	Absolute change	% change
Milk sale price					
Others	33.67	38.81	0.215		
Co-operatives	31.15	40.11	0.218	1.30**	3.35
Other household	36.12	38.62	0.215	-0.19	-0.49
Private	55.02	45.29	0.214	6.48***	16.70
Milk Value					
Others	69647.9	72880.3	958.55		
Co-operatives	90148.1	89280.4	970.05	16400***	22.50
Other household	65169.6	70562.5	955.65	-2318	-3.18
Private	92962.8	84871.2	952.45	11991***	16.45
Milk Quantity					
Others	1953.7	1990.6	25.68		
Co-operatives	2850.3	2425.6	25.99	435***	21.85
Other household	1767.7	1932.4	25.6	-58	-2.93
Private	2204.3	2309.2	25.52	319***	16.01
Total Income					
Others	178994.6	185241.3	3612.81		
Co-operatives	200815.4	194182.6	3656.16	8941***	4.83
Other household	178357.0	180836.1	3601.88	-4405**	-2.38
Private	197873.1	196506.3	3589.83	11265***	6.08
Monthly Exp					
Others	10748.5	10548.4	60.52		
Co-operatives	10715.5	10758.5	61.21	210**	1.99
Other household	10571.4	10491.8	60.32	-57	-0.54
Private	10743.7	10859.7	60.13	311***	2.95

Source: Authors estimation.

Milk Quantity

Adjusting for specification bias reveals improvement in milk quantity sold through co-operatives enables higher volume by 21.85 per cent and private channel fetches 16.01 per cent increase in milk volume. These channels enable higher volume, likely due to better aggregation and distribution systems. On the other hand, “other households” see a decline by 2.93 per cent in milk volume, further demonstrating their lack of competitiveness.

Total Income

Total income of household benefits notably from sales through private channels by 6.08 percent and in case of co-operatives it increases by 4.83 per cent. These channels help increase overall well-being by providing higher returns for milk. In contrast, selling to “other

households” leads to a marginal decline by 2.38 per cent, indicating their limited contribution to household income.

Monthly Expenditure

Monthly expenditure sees the highest increase among household selling via private channels by 2.95 per cent and by co-operatives there is increase by 1.99 per cent. These channels enhance purchasing power by improving incomes. In contrast, selling to “other households” leads to a marginal decline by 0.54 per cent, reflecting reduced economic welfare.

It is noteworthy, private channels consistently outperform other marketing options, particularly in milk prices, value and quantity, leading to better household income and expenditure. Further, co-operatives offer a balanced approach with significant gains across all welfare indicators, albeit lower than private channels. Informal channels such as “others” and “other households” exhibit inefficiencies, often resulting in lower returns and reduced welfare for producers. This analysis underscores the importance of organized marketing channels like private entities and co-operatives in enhancing economic outcomes for producers.

Conclusion

India is a world leader in the milk production since very long. Hence, the Indian dairy sector plays a significant role in the livelihoods of rural households, acting as a significant source of income and employment. Understanding the impact of marketing channels on the economic welfare of milk producers is crucial to addressing disparities and inefficiencies in the dairy value chain. The study provides a detailed analysis of the performance of different marketing channels, highlighting their influence on price realization, milk volumes, household income and expenditure, along with the socio-economic factors that drive channel selection. The findings reveal that private marketing channels are most profitable for milk producers, offering the highest price per litre and contributing significantly to household income. Cooperatives, while yielding comparatively lower prices, provide stability and support fair pricing, reliable payment systems and supplementary services like veterinary care. These features make cooperatives a vital safety net for small-scale producers. Conversely, informal channels such as direct sales to households or small traders, shows inefficiencies, with limited economic returns and reduced welfare indicators for producers. Socio-economic factors such as access to technical information, financial inclusion and education play a critical role in influencing marketing channels choices. Producers with better education play a critical role in influencing marketing channel choices. Producers with better access to resources are more likely to participate in organized channels, underscoring the need for targeted interventions to reduce barriers for marginalized groups. The study also highlights the disparities in milk productivity and market access, further emphasizing the importance of organized systems in bridging these gaps.

To improve the economic outcomes for milk producers, several policy interventions are necessary. First, investment in rural infrastructure, such as cold storage, transportation and necessary digital platforms, are essential to enhance market efficiency and reduce post-

harvest losses. Strengthening cooperatives through financial incentives, training programs and technological support will make them competitive while fostering private sector integration can bring expertise in logistics, branding and export markets. Regulatory frameworks should ensure transparency and fairness in pricing, benefitting both producer and buyers. Capacity building initiatives are crucial for empowering dairy farmers. Training programs focusing on technical knowledge, entrepreneurial skills and financial literacy can equip producers to navigate complex markets. Expanding access to credit facilities, such as Kisan Credit Cards, will enable farmers to invest in productivity-enhancing resources like better livestock and feed. Additionally, establishing centralized market information systems and grading standards will ensure transparency and equitable pricing. Inclusive policies are essential for addressing the social disparities in the dairy sector, initiatives that target women and marginalized groups, such as female-led cooperatives and community support programs, can enhance participation in organized marketing channels. Promoting financial inclusion and education for these groups will further reduce barriers and ensure equitable growth.

In conclusion, the study underscores the critical role of organized marketing channels in enhancing the welfare for milk producers in India. While private channels offer the highest economic returns, cooperatives provide much-needed stability for small-scale producers. Addressing the inefficiencies of informal channels through infrastructure development, capacity building and inclusive policies is imperative for bridging income disparities and fostering sustainable rural development. By implementing these strategies, the Indian dairy sector can achieve its full potential, ensuring improved livelihoods for producers and contributing to national food security.

Disclaimer: Views are personal.

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